

Original article

Temporomandibular joint ankylosis: patterns, management, and outcomes at a Nigerian tertiary hospital - a ten year retrospective study.

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Abstract

Background: Temporomandibular joint ankylosis (TMJA) occurs when there is fusion of the condyle to the glenoid fossa, gradually causing hypomobility of the mandible. It is mainly caused by trauma and significantly affects the masticatory system, facial skeletal development, tooth eruption, and facial aesthetics. Its treatment presents challenges, with a high risk of recurrence after surgery, which remains insufficiently studied. The study aimed to identify the pattern of TMJA presentation and management at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital. **Materials and Methods:** This retrospective study was carried out at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, a tertiary referral centre, from 2014 to 2024. Patients diagnosed with temporomandibular joint ankylosis (TMJA) were enrolled in the study. Data collected included demographic information, aetiology, TMJA type, Sawhney's classification, preoperative and postoperative interincisal distance, length of hospital stay, intubation techniques used, treatment modalities, and associated complications. **Results:** Thirty-six patients had TMJA; 16 (44.4%) were females and 20 (55.6%) were males. The mean age was 18.1 years. Trauma accounted for 72.2%, infection 19.4%, unknown cause 5.6% and previous TMJ surgery 2.8% of cases. Bilateral TMJ ankylosis was 69.4%. Sawhney's classes 2 and 3 accounted for 47.2% combined. Intubation was performed using the fiberoptic awake intubation technique in 80.6% of cases. There was no significant association in TMJ reankylosis between subjects that had gap arthroplasty as compared to those who had gap interpositional arthroplasty ($p = 0.274$). Subjects who received interpositional arthroplasty had more malocclusion after treatment ($p = 0.328$). Those with gap arthroplasty reported more aesthetic problems ($p=1.000$). **Conclusion:** TMJA is mainly post-traumatic. Interpositional arthroplasty has a slightly lower recurrence rate but a marginally higher rate of postoperative malocclusion compared to gap arthroplasty alone, although neither difference is statistically significant.

Keywords: Ankylosis, Gap arthroplasty, Interpositional arthroplasty, TMJ,

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Introduction

The Temporomandibular joint (TMJ) is unique and complex in the body because it consists of two separate synovial joints that contain an intracapsular disc.¹ It is a ginglymoarthrodial joint between the condylar head of the mandible and the articular eminence of the temporal bone, capable of rotating around multiple axes and performing translatory movements.¹ Temporomandibular joint ankylosis (TMJA) is an intracapsular condition characterised by the fusion of the bony surfaces of the joint.

Pathological bony union occurs between the condylar head of the mandible and the glenoid fossa of the temporal bone, such that movement across the joint is significantly limited or, most often, completely restricted.^{2,3} When this occurs, it is usually associated with disruptions in growth and psychological development, especially in a growing individual, which may also lead to joint dysfunction, disabling problems in mastication, digestion, speech, appearance, and maintenance of good oral hygiene, and obstructive sleep apnea syndrome (OSAS).³

Its prevalence varies depending on geographical location, with high reported rates in Africa and Asia.⁴⁻⁶ Trauma constitutes the predominant aetiology, accounting for 78% of cases; the rest is attributed to infectious, neoplastic, congenital, rheumatoid, and unknown causes.^{3,4,7} Diagnosis of TMJ ankylosis is straightforward, mainly by clinical examination and imaging studies.⁸ Orthopantomography (OPG) helps with an accurate diagnosis, while computed tomography (CT) scans with 3D reconstruction assist in determining the severity of ankylosis and visualising medial bony bridges between the mandible and skull base.^{5,8} Sawhney and colleagues, using CT images, proposed classification systems for TMJ ankylosis.⁹ The skeletal and growth changes in TMJ ankylosis patients often make restoration of jaw mobility and appearance complex and challenging.¹⁰

The treatment approach for TMJ ankylosis remains debatable, with many techniques associated with an increased risk of recurrence.^{2,11} It requires adequate excision of ankylosis mass, with or without interposition of autogenous or alloplastic material, while some have gone as far as joint replacement.^{2,12} The most frequently encountered complications in the post-operative period are restricted jaw mobility and recurrence of ankylosis.¹³ This study aims to analyse TMJA cases treated at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital over a period of 10 years.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective descriptive study enrolled TMJA cases that reported to the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Borno State, Nigeria, over 10 years, from January 2014 to December 2024. Ethical approval was waived by the Research and Ethics Committee of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital due to the retrospective nature of the study and the use of previously collected de-

identified data. All cases of TMJA managed at our facility during the study period with complete clinical records, were included in the study. Patients with incomplete records were excluded.

Medical records of subjects diagnosed with TMJA were reviewed regardless of age or gender. Extracted data included demographic details, aetiology, type and Sawhney's classification of TMJA, preoperative and postoperative level of mouth opening, length of hospital stay, intubation technique used, type of treatment and complications. Participants were categorised based on the surgical intervention received: gap arthroplasty or interpositional arthroplasty. Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were presented as frequencies and percentages, while inferential analysis was performed using Chi-square and t-tests. A p-value of <0.005 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 36 patients were recorded, with 16 (44.4%) females and 20 (55.6%) males. With a mean of 18.1 years, \pm 8.2, and an age range of 8 - 43 years. The interincisal distance (IID) at presentation was 0mm (IQR 0 - 1mm), at the immediate postoperative period 42.8 ± 3.7 mm (range 35 - 50 mm) and at 6 months 35mm (IQR 14 - 38mm), Table 1. Trauma causes that included falls from height and road traffic crashes were the most common aetiological factor, accounting for 72.2%, followed by infection 19.4%, unknown cause 5.6% and previous TMJ surgery 2.8%. Bilateral TMJ ankylosis was the predominant type, accounting for 69.4%, followed by unilateral left TMJ ankylosis, 22.2%. Sawhney type II and III were found to be jointly more common, both 47.2%. Intubation was mainly performed using the fiberoptic awake intubation technique (80.6%), as shown in Table 2. There was no statistically significant difference in the rate of TMJ reankylosis between subjects who underwent gap arthroplasty as compared to those who underwent interpositional arthroplasty ($p = 0.274$). Subjects who received interpositional arthroplasty experienced more malocclusion after treatment, but the difference was not statistically significant $p = 0.328$. Subjects who underwent gap arthroplasty reported more aesthetic problems, although this difference was also not statistically significant, $p=1.000$, Table 3.

Table 1. Age, gender, and interincisal distance at different time points.

Age	Mean 18.1years SD 8.2 Range 8 – 43
Gender	
Female	
Male	
Total	
Interincisal distance	
IID 1: At presentation	Median: 0 (IQR 0 – 1) mm
IID 2: Immediate post-operation	Mean: 42.8 mm ± SD 3.7 (range 35 – 50) mm
IID 3: 6 months post-operation	Median: 35 (14 – 38) mm

Discussion

The present study showed a slight male predominance with TMJA compared to females. This aligns with several studies reporting higher prevalence in males, which may be due to a greater incidence of trauma in males, particularly childhood condylar fractures, which is the most common cause of TMJA.

The average age at diagnosis of temporomandibular joint ankylosis (TMJA) in this study was 18.1 years (±8.2). This figure matches reports from both Jordanian and Zimbabwean populations.^{14,15} The data indicate a delay in presentation, possibly because of the slowly progressive nature of TMJA after untreated or inadequately managed trauma to the condylar region during early childhood.

According to Kaban et al., untreated or poorly managed condylar fractures in the first decade of life can result in apparent clinical ankylosis several years later.²

Trauma was found to be the primary etiological factor for temporomandibular joint ankylosis (TMJA) in this study, with falls from heights, road traffic accidents, and domestic incidents being the most common causes, followed by infectious etiologies. It is well established that trauma, particularly untreated or inadequately managed condylar fractures during childhood, plays a significant role in the development of TMJA.^{2,11,15} This association has been consistently documented in research from Africa, Asia, and the Middle East.^{4,5,15} Furthermore, in low-resource settings, infections such as otitis media is a prominent aetiologic factor, reflecting disparities in early trauma management and limited access to antibiotics.¹⁶

Table 2. Aetiology, type, Sawhney class of TMJ ankylosis, and intubation technique used.

Variable	Frequency (n=36)	Percentage (%)
Aetiology		
Trauma	26	72.2
Infection	7	19.4
Previous surgery	1	2.8
Unknown	2	5.6
Type of ankylosis		
Bilateral	25	69.4
Right unilateral	3	8.3
Left unilateral	8	22.2
Sawhney's class		
Type II	17	47.2
Type III	17	47.2
Type IV	2	5.6
Intubation		
Blind nasal	5	13.89
Tracheostomy	2	5.56
Fibreoptic	29	80.56

Table 3. Comparative analysis of recurrence rates, malocclusion incidence, and aesthetic concerns between patients treated with gap arthroplasty and interpositional arthroplasty.

Variable	Gap arthroplasty	Interpositional arthroplasty	P value
Recurrence	4 (%)	0 (%)	0.274
Malocclusion	2 (%)	3 (%)	0.328
Aesthetic problems	5 (%)	2 (%)	1.000

The results of this study demonstrated that bilateral TMJ ankylosis was the predominant type at 69.4%, contrary to most reports, which show unilateral cases due to unilateral condylar fractures following childhood trauma. Untreated condylar fractures have been linked to poor access to healthcare in low-resource settings, which may contribute to this discrepancy. Sawhney types II and III were found to be equally more common, both at 47.2%. Most studies report that intubation was mainly performed using the fibreoptic awake intubation technique (80.6%). This technique for intubation is sensitive and associated with less morbidity.

In this study, there was a slight difference in the incidence of TMJ reankylosis between subjects who underwent gap arthroplasty and those who underwent interpositional arthroplasty; however, this difference was not statistically significant. This aligns with several reports indicating similar recurrence rates when adequate removal of ankylotic mass is performed, followed by rigorous physiotherapy.^{2,15,18} Reports on reankylosis are

inconsistent; interpositional arthroplasty tends to show a lower reankylosis rate than gap arthroplasty, but this difference is not statistically significant.^{15,18}

Findings of this study revealed subjects who underwent interpositional arthroplasty exhibited greater malocclusion after treatment ($p = 0.328$), whereas those with gap arthroplasty reported more aesthetic problems ($p = 1.000$). Neither difference reached significance, and therefore, the study does not provide sufficient evidence to conclude that either surgical technique is superior or inferior with respect to re-ankylosis, postoperative malocclusion, or aesthetic outcomes. Higher malocclusion, though not statistically significant, contrasts with studies showing improved occlusion with gap arthroplasty treatment.¹⁹ Malocclusion following akylosis release might be caused by interpositional material leading to posterior gagging of occlusion and an anterior open bite, which could relapse over long-term follow-up. The greater aesthetic challenge seems plausible due to ramal shortening, although the evidence for these remains unclear and inconclusive. Future research should focus on prospective multicentre studies with standardised protocols and long-term follow-up on recurrence, occlusion, and self-reported aesthetic outcomes.

Conclusion.

TMJA is primarily post-traumatic and diagnosed through clinical examinations and imaging assessments such as OPG and CT. Despite the complexity of managing TMJA, optimal outcomes can be achieved with gap arthroplasty, with or without interpositional material, combined with coronoidectomy and rigorous postoperative physiotherapy. There is no significant difference in recurrence rates between interpositional arthroplasty and gap arthroplasty alone, although the former has lower recurrence rates. Early evaluation and management of chin trauma in children can prevent TMJA.

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Authors' Contributions

Mohammed Abdullahi, Ijakrayu Enoch Ijabani, and Fatima Babagana conceived the project and drafted the manuscript. Sakeenatu Haruna conducted the data analysis, while Kanadi Kwari and Ahmed Mohammed Alhaji supervised the methodological approach and interpretation of results. Mohammed

Abdullahi and Ahmed Mohammed Alhaji contributed to the study design and the critical interpretation of the results. Mohammed Abdullahi led the ethics application and managed the project. All authors critically revised the manuscript for intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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